

REVIEWARTICLE

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF THE THREE UNCOMMON BREEDING SHOREBIRDS IN PENINSULAR INDIA

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(Received 21 August 2024, Revised 4 September 2024, Accepted 18 September 2024)

ABSTRACT : Shorebirds, a wide group of avian species, inhabit crucial coastal areas in India for breeding and foraging and use the country as part of their migration routes along the Central Asian Flyway. The Indian peninsula boasts a rich and extensive coastline, hosting a variety of migratory shorebirds that thrive in its unique ecosystems. There are a few uncommon breeding species whose behaviors and presence have been understudied from the Indian coastlines. This review aims to comprehensively analyze three uncommon breeding shorebird species: Hanuman Plover *Charadrius seebohmi*, Little Ringed Plover *Charadrius dubius jerdoni* and the Crab Plover *Dromas ardeola* from both our field observations and the available literature. We have documented four breeding sites of the newly elevated taxon *Charadrius seebohmi*, one breeding colony with five nests of *Dromas ardeola*, marking the first documentation of this species breeding outside the Arabian Peninsula and two breeding sites of *Charadrius dubius jerdoni*. Further in-depth research is necessary to explore various aspects of these uncommon records of yet vital shorebird species' breeding biology including nesting success, hatching rates, and other relevant factors in Peninsular India.

Key words : Coastal habitats, comparative analysis, conservation, nestling, shorebirds, uncommon breeding.

How to cite : Jasmine Anand, H. Byju, S. Sheela and H. Maitreyi (2025) A comprehensive review of the three uncommon breeding shorebirds in Peninsular India. *J. Exp. Zool. India* **28**, 13-21. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.51470/jez.2025.28.1.13>

INTRODUCTION

Shorebirds, a wide variety of diverse groups of myriad avian species known for their remarkable adaptations to coastal and aquatic environments, are common along the shorelines of Peninsular India and some inland wetlands. They are known for their long-distance migrations, with many species traveling thousands of kilometers from their breeding grounds in the Arctic and sub-Arctic regions to their wintering grounds in the Indian Peninsula and other parts of South Asia (Sangha, 2021). The Indian Peninsula, with its vast coastline spanning approximately 7,500 kilometers offers a mosaic of ecological niches that attract diverse shorebird species during their breeding season (Sangha, 2021; Rashiba *et al*, 2022; Anand *et al*, 2023; Byju *et al*, 2023a). The intertidal habitats and coastal wetlands of India are a critical stopover, breeding, and wintering ground for many migratory shorebirds that breed in northern regions and use the country as part of their migration routes along the Central Asian Flyway (CAF) (Pandiyani *et al*, 2020).

Peninsular India is also home to uncommon breeding

species that are less frequently encountered but equally deserving of attention and conservation efforts (Byju *et al*, 2023 b). These uncommon breeding shorebirds are often characterized by their unique life histories, remarkable behaviours, and intriguing ecological adaptations, making them a captivating subject for conservation initiatives. Some of the common breeding shorebirds that regularly breed in the coastal and inland wetlands of India are Black-winged Stilt (*Himantopus himantopus*), Indian Stone-Curlew (*Burhinus indicus*), Greater Painted Snipe (*Rostratula benghalensis*, Yellow-wattled Lapwing (*Vanellus malabaricus*) and Red-wattled Lapwing (*Vanellus indicus*), etc. Hence, here we only emphasized the uncommon shorebirds that breed in the region. We used the term uncommon as they were not found breeding during many regular bird monitoring efforts by different groups and birders involved over several past decades.

In this review, we considered three less-studied but remarkable breeding shorebirds that breed on the shores of Peninsular India, namely, Hanuman Plover (*Charadrius*

seebohmi), Little Ringed Plover (*Charadrius dubius jerdoni*) and Crab Plover (*Dromas ardeola*). Moreover, we highlight the challenges these species face in an ever-changing environment and emphasize the importance of continued conservation efforts to ensure the survival of these fascinating and lesser-studied species of the avian world. By shedding light on these uncommon breeding shorebirds in the region, we aim to foster a greater appreciation for the biodiversity of Peninsular India and instigate actions to protect and preserve these unique and uncommon breeding species and their habitats.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

The following regions were the sites of the shorebird surveys (Fig. 1). (1) The saltwater lagoon Pillaimadam (9.28240°N, 79.10870°E), which borders Palk Bay and Rameswaram Island on the east coast of India. This

lagoon is enclosed on its landward side by grass. (2) The Dhanushkodi Lagoon (9.198580°N, 79.38330°E), on Rameswaram Island in the Gulf of Mannar (GoM) region has both mudflats and sandy areas. During the migratory season for coastal birds in the GoM region, this is one of the most important shorebirds gathering places. (3) Valinokkam is a man-made lagoon (9.16180°N, 78.62840°E), with salt pans and prawn farms. Mudflats are generated in this man-made lagoon when the excess water from these is pumped out. (4) Kodyyakadu (10.32700°N, 79.77680°E), located near the Great Vedaranyam Swamp (GVS) and Point Calimere, is surrounded by grassy sand patches. (5) Koonthankulam (8.58102°N 77.76123°E), is a protected area that abuts the tiny village of Koonthankulam in Nanguneri Taluk, Tamil Nadu, India. It is made up of the irrigation tanks Koonthankulam and Kadankulam. In South India, this is

Fig. 1 : Map showing the breeding records of uncommon shorebird species across the Peninsular India.

the biggest breeding waterbird reserve. (6) GVS (10.2792844°N, 79.7264310°E) is a coastal wetland featuring diverse habitats and ecological attributes. These include mangroves, forested wetlands, brackish to saltwater lagoons, and intertidal salt marshes.

Methodology

Our study encompasses a comprehensive survey of the peninsular region. We compiled all the documented uncommon breeding of shorebirds from our regular shorebird monitoring. We specifically focused on three uncommon breeding species, including the recently added taxon Hanuman Plover, the rarely reported breeding record of the subspecies Little Ringed Plover and the first comprehensive investigation of the enigmatic Crab Plover from the region. The records are collected from southeast coast through bird census and surveys in collaboration with the forest department from 2017 to 2023 and a few undocumented inland wetlands through our field observations and avian surveys. Furthermore, we reviewed the published literature from the region to update the breeding locations of all three mentioned species. We considered the record until the 1990s historical and from 2000 as current observations. The analysis focuses on species infrequently observed during the breeding season along the coastal habitats. All our shorebird surveys were done with the regular monitoring protocol of reaching the scanning points at each location and waiting for five to ten minutes at each scanning point to get the birds to acclimatized with us and then observe the species (Howes and Bakewell, 1989; Bibby *et al.*, 2000). Whenever, we see shorebird breeding sites, we keep a safe distance from them to avoid disturbing the nest or eggs, as may be the case. Only in GVS, we conducted a boat survey. Following the discovery of the species during boat surveys, then foot surveys were carried out to identify the exact nesting site. The activities were captured using a Canon 400 mm telephoto camera and 10x50 Nikon binoculars.

RESULTS

We present the findings of all three important and uncommon breeding shorebird species for a better understanding. We include the historical data of breeding sites with months and years of observation from the available literature along with the current breeding site observation records in Table 1.

Species account

Hanuman Plover

Hanuman Plover (*Charadrius seebohmi*) (Fig. 2A) is the most recent bird to be added to the list of shorebirds

worldwide. The subspecies *Charadrius alexandrinus seebohmi* of the Kentish Plover was recently reevaluated for systematic classification based on phenotypic traits and genetic distinctiveness in comparison to the migrant species *Charadrius alexandrinus* and *C. dealbatus* which resulted in the elevation of the subspecies to full species status and designated a new taxon (Niroshan *et al.*, 2023). Kentish Plover has a widespread range and has breeding populations on every continent except Antarctica (del Hoyo *et al.*, 1996; Wetlands International, 2006; Meininger *et al.*, 2009; Vincze *et al.*, 2013). Kentish Plover is prevalent in the subcontinent (Sangha, 2021) and the breeding population is documented from South India and Maharashtra (Krebs, 1956; Mellufish, 1966; Ali and Ripley, 1983; Futehally, 2006). Table 1 lists Hanuman Plover's breeding locations based on our observations and information from the literature.

During the breeding season, Hanuman Plover exhibits distinctive changes in their plumage in comparison to Kentish Plover's nominate race which reaches the GoM by September and departs by mid-March (Balachandran, 1995). In breeding plumage, the black fore-crown of Hanuman Plover becomes darker, and the eye stripe undergoes modification during this period. The legs are dark grey in *C. seebohmi* and black in *C. alexandrinus*. The breeding season of Hanuman Plover typically spans from February to July, primarily within coastal areas and dry mudflats. Balachandran (1995) reported the breeding activities between April and July in GoM. Our study corroborates these findings, with recorded instances of breeding activity commencing as early as February. Our detailed breeding records from various sites provide valuable insights into the nesting habits of this species. Notably, Hanuman Plover adults were first observed as early as February 24, 2017, in Dhanushkodi. Furthermore, our observations extend to March 2017, when nesting was documented in both Dhanushkodi and Valinokkam. Subsequently, in Pillaimadam, we sighted an adult Hanuman Plover with two chicks on June 15, 2022 (Byju *et al.*, 2023c). Additionally, we recorded breeding activities in the same location on June 10, 2023. Apart from GoM, we documented two eggs in a nest with adult incubation in Kodyyakadu, near Point Calimere, in February 2020. In Dhanushkodi (2017) and Valinokkam (2017 and 2020), we documented the clutch containing three eggs (Fig. 2B). In 2023, there were only two eggs in Valinokkam. In Pillaimadam, the clutch had two eggs in February 2020 and 2023. In Kodyyakadu, two eggs were seen in the nests in 2020. These comprehensive records contribute to the Hanuman Plover's nesting season in these coastal and mudflat habitats.

Table 1 : Breeding sites and coordinates (recent and historical records) of uncommon shorebird species in Peninsular India. (* Months of these records are unavailable; † Recent records).

S.	Common Name	Scientific Name	Nesting Sites	GPS Coordinates	Month & Year of Breeding Records no.
1	Hanuman Plover	<i>Charadrius seebohmi</i>	† Pillaimadam, East coast	9.28240 °N 79.10870 °E	June 2022; June 2023
2	Hanuman Plover	<i>Charadrius seebohmi</i>	† Dhanushkodi, East coast	9.198580 °N 79.38330 °E	February 2017
3	Hanuman Plover	<i>Charadrius seebohmi</i>	† Valinokkam, East Coast	9.16180 °N 78.62840 °E	March 2017
4	Hanuman Plover	<i>Charadrius seebohmi</i>	† Kodiyakadu, East coast	10.32700 °N 79.77680 °E	February 2020
5	Crab Plover	<i>Dromas ardeola</i>	† Great Vedaranyam Swamp, East coast	10.2792844 °N 79.7264310 °E	July 2023
6	Little Ringed Plover	<i>Charadrius dubius jerdoni</i>	† Dharapuram, Inland wetland	10.7789 °N 77.4215 °E	October 2022
7	Little Ringed Plover	<i>Charadrius dubius jerdoni</i>	† Koonthankulam, Inland wetland	8.58102 °N 77.76123 °E	April 2023
8	Hanuman Plover	<i>Charadrius seebohmi</i>	Point Calimere, East coast	10.2864 °N 79.8299 °E	January 2006
9	Hanuman Plover	<i>Charadrius seebohmi</i>	Vidarbha, Maharashtra. Inland wetland	20.011 °N 3.8233 °E	May 2003
10	Hanuman Plover	<i>Charadrius seebohmi</i>	Vani vilasa sagara - Karnataka, West coast	13.891466 °N 76.477886 °E	May 2017
11	Hanuman Plover	<i>Charadrius seebohmi</i>	Cuddalore, East coast	11.753460 °N 79.759560 °E	1956*
12	Hanuman Plover	<i>Charadrius seebohmi</i>	Chengalpettu, East coast	12.9758 °N 80.2205 °E	May 1966
13	Little Ringed Plover	<i>Charadrius dubius jerdoni</i>	Chittur, Palakkad	10.576585 °N 76.692466 °E	1992*
14	Little Ringed Plover	<i>Charadrius dubius jerdoni</i>	Kudallur, Palakkad	10.495808 °N 76.043021 °E	1992*
15	Little Ringed Plover	<i>Charadrius dubius jerdoni</i>	Attur, Inland wetland	11.664325 °N 78.146011 °E	1956*

Hanuman plovers are ground-nesting birds (Byju *et al*, 2023c) favour low, open, and damp nesting sites away from dense vegetation and human disturbances. We noted that their nests typically comprised shallow scrapes partially filled with materials like pebbles, small snail shells, fragments of dry mud, and nearby vegetation. These nests were predominantly located in areas created by small water puddles near lagoons or the main water bodies. Identifying the nests proved challenging, requiring patient observation of pairs in breeding plumage near the nesting sites. Furthermore, we observed adult plovers protecting their newly hatched chicks, with both parents patrolling and caring for the offspring during the initial weeks of hatching. The breeding system of Hanuman Plovers was similar to that of Kentish Plovers, exhibiting intriguing diversity (Székely *et al*, 2006). While both parents take

turns incubating the eggs, the situation changes once the eggs hatch. One parent, typically the female, may abandon the family to find a new mate, leading to diverse mating patterns within a single population, such as monogamy, polygyny, and polyandry (Lessells, 1984; Kosztolányi and Székely, 2002; Székely *et al*, 2006). Our observations of nests of Hanuman Plovers found that the pairs adhered to a consistent schedule of attending to their nests.

Crab Plover

The Crab Plover (family Dromadidae) (Fig. 2C) represents a distinct and intriguing species exclusively found along the subtropical and tropical coastlines bordering the Indian Ocean and are recognized as winter migrants and are frequently observed along the coasts of Peninsular India, Gujarat, Lakshadweep and Andaman and Nicobar Islands of India, Bangladesh, Maldives,

Fig. 2 : (A) Little Ringed Plover and (B) Nestling of Little Ringed Plover at Dharapuram (C) Crab Plover and (D) Nest of Crab Plover at GVS, (E) Hanuman Plover and (F) Egg of Hanuman Plover at Dhanushkodi.

Pakistan and Northern Sri Lanka during the winter months. The breeding habitats of Crab Plovers are documented from various islands in both the Arabian Gulf and Africa. These breeding locations encompass regions within Egypt, Eritrea, Iran, Kuwait, Masirah Island of Oman, islets of Northern Somalia, Saudi Arabia, Sudan, and United Arab Emirates (Cramp *et al*, 1983; De Marchi, *et al*, 2006; Scott, 2007; Delany *et al*, 2009; Behrouzi-Rad and Behrouzi-Rad, 2010; Jennings, 2010; Tayefeh *et al*, 2011; Javed *et al*, 2012; Tayefeh *et al*, 2013; Bom and Al-Nasrallah, 2015; Abdelhafez *et al*, 2020).

The breeding season of Crab Plovers typically occurs from April to August (Morris, 1992; Hockey, 1995; Rands, 1996), with slight variations based on the specific region within the Arabian Peninsula and Africa where they nest. In the Persian Gulf, breeding begins in April (Cramp *et al*, 1985; Javed *et al*, 2012), while in the Red Sea along the African coast, it starts two or three weeks later (De Marchi *et al*, 2006). The new breeding record of Crab Plover from GVS of the Indian southeast coast also has the same breeding season (Byju *et al*, 2023b).

Crab Plovers lay a single egg within a self-dug burrow on a flat sandbank (Figure 2D) (Morris, 1992; Hockey, 1995; Rands, 1996). The nesting behaviour of the Plover involves several distinctive features. The nesting colony site must be suitable for burrow digging, which requires

deep soil or flat to gently sloping sandbanks (Hockey and Aspinall, 1997; Chiozzi *et al*, 2011). Additionally, easy access to and from colony sites is crucial, near the sea and in open spaces (Cramp *et al*, 1985). They generally avoid nesting areas with tall and dense vegetation (De Marchi *et al*, 2006). Vegetative cover is essential in loose soils to reduce the risk of burrow collapse. At the end of their burrows, crab plovers construct unlined chambers that range in depth from 100 to 250 centimeters. These chambers are dug into sandy substrates close to the bases of shrubs (del Hoyo *et al*, 1996), taking advantage of the stabilizing effect that the roots of the shrubs have on burrow entrance (Burgeois *et al*, 2008; Chiozzi *et al*, 2011). This nesting strategy provides crucial protection and security for the eggs during incubation. Moreover, these burrows have been noted to enable limited solar incubation (De Marchi *et al*, 2008) and support extended foraging on tidal food resources (De Marchi *et al*, 2015).

A small colony of Crab Plovers consisting of five nests was first discovered in July 2023, close to the sea, and occupied a relatively compact area spanning approximately 100-150 m². The offspring of the Crab Plovers are semi-nidifugous, meaning they remain within the nest burrow until they are ready to fledge (Hockey and Aspinall, 1997). The breeding biology of the Crab Plover is characterized by several unique features among shorebirds as it is the only species that construct a self-dug burrow for nesting and it lays eggs with a distinctive white colouration (Rands, 1996; Hockey and Aspinall, 1997). It is the only waterbird species documented that provides food to its chicks well beyond the post-breeding period (De Sanctis *et al*, 2005). These distinctive traits contribute to the species' remarkable ecological niche within the avian community.

Little Ringed Plover

Little Ringed Plover (*Charadrius dubius*) (Fig. 2E) comprises three distinct subspecies: *Charadrius dubius curonicus*, *Charadrius dubius dubius* and *Charadrius dubius jerdoni*. Notably, *C.d. jerdoni* is a resident to the Indian Subcontinent and Southeast Asia (Kirby and Scott, 2009). Recent breeding records of this species in southern India are sparse, with notable exceptions observed in locations such as Uppar dam, Dharapuram (Byju *et al*, 2023d), and in our study has been documented in Koonthamkulam, both in Tamil Nadu.

These breeding seasons of the subspecies have varied in the Indian subcontinent from May and June (Wilson, 1899); June in Himachal (Whistler, 1926); February -March in Jawai Dam and April-May in Tal Chhappar, Churu, and Jaipur of Rajasthan (Sangha, 2021);

March-May; June and November in Palakkad, Kerala (Neelakantan, 1992), October-November in Dharapuram, Tamil Nadu (Byju *et al*, 2023d) and April in Koonthamkulam, Tamil Nadu. In a breeding season, two or three broods are raised. The female lays two to three eggs in a clutch. The eggs are small and shaped like a peg-top. The eggs are dull with black dots. We noted that the incubation period lasted 17 days. The female and male both incubate the egg.

During April 2023 in Koonthamkulam, three nests and nestlings were documented (Fig. 2F). Little Ringed Plover exhibits distinctive features in breeding plumage and displays a yellow eye ring encircling its eyes, while the black neck ring becomes more pronounced and thicker. To distinguish *C.d.jerdoni* from the other two subspecies, one can look for a forehead with a notable white patch and a forecrown with black colouring. Additionally, *C.d.jerdoni* stands out with a broader yolk-yellow orbital ring (Hayman *et al*, 2021). During their breeding season, Little Ringed Plovers tend to favour habitats characterized by open, sandy, or pebbly shores adjacent to shallow-standing freshwater pools, lakes, river islands, and slow-flowing rivers. They also commonly nest in dry, riverbeds with stones and areas within dune depressions (Johnsgard, 1981; Cramp *et al*, 1983; del Hoyo *et al*, 1996; Grimmett *et al*, 1998). The nest that we encountered was a slight indentation in the ground close to the water's edge. Notably, we noted an interesting behaviour in which the bird, engaged in constant flight and exploration around the damp ground, utilized its small, nearly-shed feathers from its abdominal region as insulation for the nest. Sometimes, they make their nests on the rocky ground with the help of small stones that harmonize with their surroundings.

Eventhough, Hanuman Plover is documented from many coastal wetlands including Kochi on the western coast, Kollam, Rameswaram, Point Calimere, Cuddalore, and Chengalpattu on the east coast (Niroshan *et al* 2023), breeding records are only from Rameswaram and Point Calimere regions (Byju *et al*, 2023c). This underscores the possibility that this species may be breeding in alternative wetland habitats within Peninsular India and the need for a comprehensive survey and monitoring initiative across Peninsular India to establish specific breeding sites for conservation endeavours and to assess the species' status. The classification of *C. seebohmi* as a regional endemic holds significant implications for protection prioritization in the CAF in Sri Lanka (Abeyrama and Seneviratne, 2018) and southern India, potentially elevating this species to a flagship species for conservation initiatives.

Despite the well-documented Crab Plover breeding occurrences in the Arabian Peninsula and Africa, the finding of the first confirmed breeding site in India-beyond the species' primary range- is a significant discovery. This colony appears to be a recent establishment, as indicated by the absence of prior records and the relatively small number of nests compared to the Middle-Eastern colonies. Consequently, this sighting calls for in-depth and comprehensive research efforts.

The limited breeding records of the Little Ringed Plover, confined to just two breeding sites in Tamil Nadu, suggest the possibility of unexplored breeding areas. The restricted range and distribution may warrant consideration of this subspecies as a distinct species (Sangha, 2021).

Conservation issues and strategies

Southern India and Sri Lanka, home to many rare species are recognized as global hotspots for biodiversity (Myers *et al*, 2000; Mittermeier *et al*, 2004). It is critical to safeguard breeding habitats, especially those that are not designated protected zones. By acknowledging *C. seebohmi* as a regional endemic species, it is imperative to recognize that these breeding plovers have a limited breeding and wintering range. The breeding grounds of *C. seebohmi* face an additional challenge due to the notably high human population density in the region (Luck, 2007; MoMDE, 2019). The relentless destruction of habitat, like encroachment, pollution, etc. and the relentless pursuit of economic development, like highways, ports, and wind farms, pose significant threats to the survival of this species. Another threat to the Hanuman Plover's survival is the existence of stray dogs and children gathering eggs. Awareness campaigns and education initiatives can address some of these issues.

Eventhough the breeding range of Crab Plover has been restricted to a small number of colonies adjacent to habitats experiencing pollution and coastal changes, posing serious risks to the breeding areas, no direct threats have been observed for the breeding birds in GVS. We encountered no evidence of egg collection by fishermen, despite reports of such activities at other nesting sites, including those in the Arabian Peninsula (Rands, 1996) and worries about the introduction of rats and cats to breeding sites (De Marchi *et al* 2006; Javed *et al* 2012), were observed in our breeding habitat. An indirect threat emerged through interaction with the local fishing community about outsiders' access to the island, especially in the summer months (June -July), which coincided with Crab Plover's breeding season as many of these tourists pay local boatmen for unapproved days trips to the island.

Since the Crab Plover nesting colonies are located in vegetated areas along the shores, where fishermen frequently dock their small fishing vessels, there is a risk of unintentional disturbance, potentially leading to the trampling of burrows and damage to eggs.

The breeding record of Little Ringed Plover subspecies *C. d. jerdoni* at Uppar Dam and Koonthamkulam, both in Tamil Nadu hold immense significance. These inland wetlands play a vital role as breeding grounds for numerous shorebirds. It's a critical habitat for various threatened waterbird species during their migration. Beyond its rich avian diversity, the Uppar Dam region is undergoing significant changes. Many local property owners are altering barren land for real estate sales, destroying vital habitats. These breeding records highlight the importance of preserving and conserving such vital habitats in the face of increasing urbanization and habitat loss.

CONCLUSION

Prioritizing the conservation of regional endemics such as *C. seebohmi* holds significant promise for the conservation of vital ecosystems. This conservation focus should benefit migratory and resident shorebirds, potentially yielding positive outcomes for millions of human communities. The rapid transformation of habitats across India, driven by diverse economic factors, emphasizes the urgency of conducting extensive wetland surveys throughout the Peninsular region. This imperative is particularly underscored by the discovery of a few uncommon breeding species from varied locations spread over a few hundred kilometers including Hanuman Plover, Little Ringed Plover and Crab Plover species, which emphasizes the significance of safeguarding their habitats.

Declaration of Competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper

Funding : Not applicable.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We acknowledge Mr. Raveendran N and Mr. Somu Prasad, who assisted in the fieldwork and the boatman and the Tamil Nadu forest department officials for assisting us during surveys.

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